

Introduction to Neutrosophic Nearrings

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Abstract

In this paper, we introduce the concept of neutrosophic nearrings. Elementary properties of neutrosophic nearrings are presented.

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1 Introduction

Let $(N, +, \cdot)$ be a set with two binary operations $+$ and $\cdot$. N is called a left nearring if the following conditions hold:

- (1) $(N, +)$ is a group, not necessarily abelian.
- (2) $(N, \cdot)$ is a semigroup.
- (3) For all $x, y, z \in N$, $x(y + z) = xy + xz$.

A right nearring is similarly defined. If $(N, +)$ is an abelian group, then $(N, +, \cdot)$ is called an abelian nearring. Also, if $(N, \cdot)$ is commutative, then $(N, +, \cdot)$ is called a commutative nearring.

In 1995, F. Smarandache introduced the concept of neutrosophic logic as an extension of fuzzy logic (see [9],[10], [11]). In 2006, Vasantha Kandasamy and F. Smarandache introduced the concept of neutrosophic algebraic structures (see [14],[15], [16],[17]). Since then, several researchers have studied the concepts and a great deal of literature has been produced (see [1],[2],[3],[4],[5],[6],[7]).

Let X be a nonempty set and let I be an indeterminate. The set

$$X(I) = \langle X, I \rangle = \{(x, yI) : x, y \in X\} \quad (1)$$

is called a neutrosophic set generated by X and I . If $+$ and $\cdot$ are ordinary addition and multiplication, I has the following properties:

- (1) $I + I + \cdots + I = nI$.
- (2) $I + (-I) = 0$.
- (3) $I.I \cdots .I = I^n = I$ for all positive integer n .
- (4) $0.I = 0$.
- (5) I^{-1} is undefined and therefore does not exist.

If $*$: $X(I) \times X(I) \rightarrow X(I)$ is a binary operation defined on $X(I)$, then the couple $(X(I), *)$ is called a neutrosophic algebraic structure and it is named according the axioms satisfied by $*$. If $(X(I), *)$ and $(Y(I), *')$ are two neutrosophic algebraic structures, the mapping $\phi : (X(I), *) \rightarrow (Y(I), *')$ is called a neutrosophic homomorphism if the following conditions hold:

- (1) $\phi((w, xI) * (y, zI)) = \phi((w, xI)) *' \phi((y, zI))$.
- (2) $\phi(I) = I \quad \forall (w, xI), (y, zI) \in X(I)$.

2 Main Results

Definition 2.1. Let $(N, +, \cdot)$ be any left nearring. The triple $(N(I), +, \cdot)$ is called a neutrosophic left nearring. For all $(a, bI), (c, dI) \in N(I)$, we define:

$$(a, bI) + (c, dI) = (a + c, (b + d)I). \quad (2)$$

$$-(a, bI) = (-a, -bI). \quad (3)$$

$$(a, bI) \cdot (c, dI) = (ac, (ad + bc + bd)I). \quad (4)$$

0, the zero element in $(N, +)$ is represented by $(0, 0)$ in $(N(I), +)$. Any element $x \in N$ is represented by $(x, 0)$ in $N(I)$. I in $N(I)$ is sometimes represented by $(0, I)$ in $N(I)$.

Except otherwise stated, all nearrings in this paper will be left nearrings and all neutrosophic nearrings will be neutrosophic left nearrings.

Example 1. Let $(X(I), +)$ be a neutrosophic group and let $M^{X(I)}$ be a neutrosophic set defined by

$$M^{X(I)} = \{\phi : X(I) \rightarrow X(I)\}.$$

For all $\phi, \psi \in M^{X(I)}$, define:

$$\begin{aligned} (\phi + \psi)((x, yI)) &= \phi((x, yI)) + \psi((x, yI)) \\ \phi \circ \psi((x, yI)) &= \phi(\psi((x, yI))) \quad \forall (x, yI) \in X(I). \end{aligned}$$

Then $(M^{X(I)}, +, \circ)$ is a neutrosophic nearring.

Example 2. Let

$$N(I) = \{(0, 0), (a, 0), (b, 0), (c, 0), (a, aI), (a, bI), (a, cI), (b, aI), (b, bI), (b, cI), (c, aI), (c, bI), (c, cI), (0, aI), (0, bI), (0, cI)\}$$

be a neutrosophic set and let $+$ and $\cdot$ be binary operations defined on $N(I)$ as shown in the cayley tables below.

$+$	(0, 0)	(a, 0)	(b, 0)	(c, 0)	(a, aI)	(a, bI)	(a, cI)	(b, aI)
(0, 0)	(0, 0)	(a, 0)	(b, 0)	(c, 0)	(a, aI)	(a, bI)	(a, cI)	(b, aI)
(a, 0)	(a, 0)	(0, 0)	(c, 0)	(b, 0)	(0, aI)	(0, bI)	(0, cI)	(c, aI)
(b, 0)	(b, 0)	(c, 0)	(0, 0)	(a, 0)	(c, aI)	(c, bI)	(c, cI)	(0, aI)
(c, 0)	(c, 0)	(b, 0)	(a, 0)	(0, 0)	(b, aI)	(b, bI)	(b, cI)	(a, aI)
(a, aI)	(a, aI)	(0, aI)	(c, aI)	(b, aI)	(0, 0)	(0, cI)	(0, bI)	(c, 0)
(a, bI)	(a, bI)	(0, bI)	(c, bI)	(b, bI)	(0, cI)	(0, 0)	(0, aI)	(c, cI)
(a, cI)	(a, cI)	(0, cI)	(c, cI)	(b, cI)	(0, bI)	(0, aI)	(0, 0)	(c, bI)
(b, aI)	(b, aI)	(c, aI)	(0, aI)	(a, aI)	(c, 0)	(c, cI)	(c, bI)	(0, 0)
(b, bI)	(b, bI)	(c, bI)	(0, bI)	(a, bI)	(c, cI)	(c, 0)	(c, aI)	(0, cI)
(b, cI)	(b, cI)	(c, cI)	(0, cI)	(a, cI)	(c, bI)	(c, aI)	(c, 0)	(0, bI)
(c, aI)	(c, aI)	(b, aI)	(a, aI)	(0, aI)	(b, 0)	(b, cI)	(b, bI)	(a, 0)
(c, bI)	(c, bI)	(b, bI)	(a, bI)	(0, bI)	(b, cI)	(b, 0)	(b, aI)	(a, cI)
(c, cI)	(c, cI)	(b, cI)	(c, cI)	(0, cI)	(b, bI)	(b, aI)	(b, 0)	(a, bI)
(0, aI)	(0, aI)	(a, aI)	(b, aI)	(c, aI)	(a, 0)	(a, cI)	(a, bI)	(b, 0)
(0, bI)	(0, bI)	(a, bI)	(b, bI)	(c, bI)	(a, cI)	(a, 0)	(a, aI)	(b, cI)
(0, cI)	(0, cI)	(a, cI)	(b, cI)	(c, cI)	(a, bI)	(a, aI)	(a, 0)	(b, bI)

$+$	(b, bI)	(b, cI)	(c, aI)	(c, bI)	(c, cI)	(0, aI)	(0, bI)	(0, cI)
(0, 0)	(b, bI)	(b, cI)	(c, aI)	(c, bI)	(c, cI)	(0, aI)	(0, bI)	(0, cI)
(a, 0)	(c, bI)	(c, cI)	(b, aI)	(b, bI)	(b, cI)	(a, aI)	(a, bI)	(a, cI)
(b, 0)	(0, bI)	(0, cI)	(a, aI)	(a, bI)	(a, cI)	(b, aI)	(b, bI)	(b, cI)
(c, 0)	(a, bI)	(a, cI)	(0, aI)	(0, bI)	(0, cI)	(c, aI)	(c, bI)	(c, cI)
(a, aI)	(c, cI)	(c, bI)	(c, 0)	(b, cI)	(b, bI)	(a, 0)	(a, cI)	(a, bI)
(a, bI)	(c, 0)	(c, aI)	(b, cI)	(b, 0)	(b, aI)	(a, cI)	(a, 0)	(a, aI)
(a, cI)	(c, aI)	(c, 0)	(b, bI)	(b, aI)	(b, 0)	(a, bI)	(a, aI)	(a, 0)
(b, aI)	(0, cI)	(0, bI)	(a, 0)	(a, cI)	(a, bI)	(b, 0)	(b, cI)	(b, bI)
(b, bI)	(0, 0)	(0, aI)	(a, cI)	(a, 0)	(a, aI)	(b, cI)	(b, 0)	(b, aI)
(b, cI)	(0, aI)	(0, 0)	(a, bI)	(a, aI)	(a, 0)	(b, bI)	(b, aI)	(b, 0)
(c, aI)	(a, cI)	(a, bI)	(0, 0)	(0, cI)	(0, bI)	(c, 0)	(c, cI)	(c, bI)
(c, bI)	(a, 0)	(a, aI)	(0, cI)	(0, 0)	(0, aI)	(c, cI)	(c, 0)	(c, aI)
(c, cI)	(a, aI)	(a, 0)	(0, bI)	(0, aI)	(0, 0)	(c, bI)	(c, aI)	(c, 0)
(0, aI)	(b, cI)	(b, bI)	(c, 0)	(c, cI)	(c, bI)	(0, 0)	(0, cI)	(0, bI)
(0, bI)	(b, 0)	(b, aI)	(c, cI)	(c, 0)	(c, aI)	(0, cI)	(0, 0)	(0, aI)
(0, cI)	(b, aI)	(b, 0)	(c, bI)	(c, aI)	(c, 0)	(0, bI)	(0, aI)	(0, 0)

.	(0, 0)	(a, 0)	(b, 0)	(c, 0)	(a, aI)	(a, bI)	(a, cI)	(b, aI)
(0, 0)	(0, 0)	(0, 0)	(0, 0)	(0, 0)	(0, 0)	(0, 0)	(0, 0)	(0, 0)
(a, 0)	(0, 0)	(a, 0)	(0, 0)	(a, 0)	(a, aI)	(a, 0)	(a, aI)	(0, aI)
(b, 0)	(0, 0)	(0, 0)	(0, 0)	(0, 0)	(0, 0)	(0, 0)	(0, 0)	(0, 0)
(c, 0)	(0, 0)	(c, 0)	(0, 0)	(c, 0)	(c, cI)	(c, 0)	(c, cI)	(0, cI)
(a, aI)	(0, 0)	(a, aI)	(0, aI)	(a, aI)	(a, 0)	(a, aI)	(a, aI)	(0, 0)
(a, bI)	(0, 0)	(a, 0)	(0, 0)	(a, 0)	(a, aI)	(a, 0)	(a, aI)	(0, aI)
(a, cI)	(0, 0)	(a, cI)	(0, 0)	(a, cI)	(a, aI)	(a, cI)	(a, aI)	(0, bI)
(b, aI)	(0, 0)	(0, aI)	(0, 0)	(0, aI)	(0, 0)	(0, aI)	(0, 0)	(0, aI)
(b, bI)	(0, 0)	(0, 0)	(0, 0)	(0, 0)	(0, 0)	(0, 0)	(0, 0)	(0, 0)
(b, cI)	(0, 0)	(0, cI)	(0, 0)	(0, cI)	(0, 0)	(0, cI)	(0, 0)	(0, cI)
(c, aI)	(0, 0)	(c, aI)	(0, 0)	(c, aI)	(c, cI)	(c, aI)	(c, cI)	(0, bI)
(c, bI)	(0, 0)	(c, 0)	(0, 0)	(c, 0)	(c, cI)	(c, 0)	(c, cI)	(0, cI)
(c, cI)	(0, 0)	(c, cI)	(0, 0)	(c, cI)	(c, cI)	(c, cI)	(c, cI)	(0, 0)
(0, aI)	(0, 0)	(0, aI)	(0, 0)	(0, aI)	(0, 0)	(0, aI)	(0, 0)	(0, aI)
(0, bI)	(0, 0)	(0, 0)	(0, 0)	(0, 0)	(0, 0)	(0, 0)	(0, 0)	(0, 0)
(0, cI)	(0, 0)	(0, cI)	(0, 0)	(0, cI)	(0, 0)	(0, cI)	(0, 0)	(0, cI)

.	(b, bI)	(b, cI)	(c, aI)	(c, bI)	(c, cI)	(0, aI)	(0, bI)	(0, cI)
(0, 0)	(0, 0)	(0, 0)	(0, 0)	(0, 0)	(0, 0)	(0, 0)	(0, 0)	(0, 0)
(a, 0)	(0, 0)	(0, aI)	(a, aI)	(a, 0)	(a, aI)	(0, aI)	(0, 0)	(0, aI)
(b, 0)	(0, 0)	(0, 0)	(0, 0)	(0, 0)	(0, 0)	(0, 0)	(0, 0)	(0, 0)
(c, 0)	(0, 0)	(0, cI)	(c, cI)	(c, 0)	(c, cI)	(0, cI)	(0, 0)	(0, cI)
(a, aI)	(0, 0)	(0, 0)	(a, aI)	(a, aI)	(a, aI)	(0, 0)	(0, 0)	(0, 0)
(a, bI)	(0, 0)	(0, aI)	(a, aI)	(a, 0)	(a, aI)	(0, aI)	(0, 0)	(0, aI)
(a, cI)	(0, 0)	(0, bI)	(a, aI)	(a, cI)	(a, aI)	(0, bI)	(0, 0)	(0, bI)
(b, aI)	(0, 0)	(0, aI)						
(b, bI)	(0, 0)	(0, 0)	(0, 0)	(0, 0)	(0, 0)	(0, 0)	(0, 0)	(0, 0)
(b, cI)	(0, 0)	(0, cI)						
(c, aI)	(0, 0)	(0, bI)	(c, cI)	(c, aI)	(c, cI)	(0, bI)	(0, 0)	(0, bI)
(c, bI)	(0, 0)	(0, cI)	(c, cI)	(c, 0)	(c, cI)	(0, cI)	(0, 0)	(0, cI)
(c, cI)	(0, 0)	(0, 0)	(c, cI)	(c, cI)	(c, cI)	(0, cI)	(0, 0)	(0, 0)
(0, aI)	(0, 0)	(0, aI)	(0, 0)	(0, aI)	(0, aI)	(0, aI)	(0, 0)	(0, aI)
(0, bI)	(0, 0)	(0, 0)	(0, 0)	(0, 0)	(0, 0)	(0, 0)	(0, 0)	(0, 0)
(0, cI)	(0, 0)	(0, cI)	(0, 0)	(0, cI)	(0, cI)	(0, cI)	(0, 0)	(0, cI)

Then $(N(I), +, \cdot)$ is a neutrosophic nearring.

Theorem 2.2. *Let $(N(I), +, \cdot)$ be a neutrosophic nearring. Then $N(I)$ is a nearring if and only if $(N, +)$ is an abelian group.*

Proof. Suppose that $N(I)$ is a nearring. Obviously, $(N, +)$ is an abelian group. Conversely, suppose that $(N, +)$ is an abelian group. Let $(a, bI), (c, dI), (e, fI)$ be arbitrary elements in $N(I)$. Then:

(1) $(a, bI) + (c, dI) = (a + c, (b + d)I) \in N(I)$.

(2)

$$\begin{aligned}
(a, bI) + ((c, dI) + (e, fI)) &= (a, bI) + (c + e, (d + f)I) \\
&= (a + (c + e), (b + (d + f))I) \\
&= ((a + c) + e, ((b + d) + f)I) \\
&= ((a, bI) + (c, dI)) + (e, fI).
\end{aligned}$$

(3)

$$\begin{aligned}
(a, bI) + (0, 0) &= (a + 0, (b + 0)I) \\
&= (a, bI).
\end{aligned}$$

Similarly, $(0, 0) + (a, bI) = (a, bI)$. Thus, $(0, 0)$ is a zero element of $(N(I), +)$.

(4)

$$\begin{aligned}
(a, bI) + (-a, -bI) &= (a + (-a), (b + (-b))I) \\
&= (0, 0I) \\
&= (0, 0).
\end{aligned}$$

Similarly, $(-a, -bI) + (a, bI) = (0, 0)$. Thus, $(-a, -bI)$ is an additive inverse of (a, bI) .

Accordingly, $(N(I), +)$ is a group.

(5)

$$\begin{aligned}
(a, bI) \cdot ((c, dI) \cdot (e, fI)) &= (a, bI) \cdot (ce, (cf + de + df)I) \\
&= (a(ce), (a(cf + de + df) + b(ce) + b(cf + de + df))I) \\
&= ((ace), (acf + ade + adf + bce + bcf + bde + bdf)I). \\
((a, bI) \cdot (c, dI)) \cdot (e, fI) &= (ac, (ad + bc + bd)I) \cdot (e, fI) \\
&= ((ac)e, ((ac)f + (ad + bc + bd)e + (ad + bc + bd)f)I) \\
&= (ace, (acf + ade + bce + bde + adf + bcf + bdf)I).
\end{aligned}$$

Since $(N, +)$ is abelian, we have $acf + ade + adf + bce + bcf + bde + bdf = acf + ade + bce + bde + adf + bcf + bdf$. Hence $(N(I), \cdot)$ is a semigroup.

(6)

$$\begin{aligned}
(a, bI) \cdot (c, dI) + (e, fI) &= (a, bI) \cdot (c + e, (d + f)I) \\
&= (a(c + e), (a(d + f) + b(c + e) + b(d + f))I) \\
&= (ac + ae, (ad + af + bc + be + bd + bf)I). \\
(a, bI) \cdot (c, dI) + (a, bI) \cdot (e, fI) &= (ac, (ad + bc + bd)I) + (ae, (af + be + bf)I) \\
&= (ac + ae, (ad + bc + bd + af + be + bf)I).
\end{aligned}$$

Since $(N, +)$ is abelian, it follows that $ad + af + bc + be + bd + bf = ad + bc + bd + af + be + bf$ and therefore $(a, bI) \cdot (c, dI) + (e, fI) = (a, bI) \cdot (c, dI) + (a, bI) \cdot (e, fI)$. Hence, $(N(I), +, \cdot)$ is a nearring. $\square$

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